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ENVIRONMENT PROTECTION THROUGH GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNANCE FOR SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS

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Abstract

Global warming has far reaching impact on all walks of life across the globe. The man made mistakes are the main cause for global temperature is raising which serious issue of concern for world leaders and policy makers. Business and industry has been treated as main culprit responsible for raising temperature where people argue that it is Business and industry are contributories to carbon dioxide, methane and other toxic gases and wastes to environment leading green house formation. There are number of legislative measures both at international and national levels pressurizing business and industry to follow sustainable business policies to protect and preserve the environment. In India, under corporate governance mechanism and CSR philosophy Indian corporate sector is forced to follow environment protection guidelines to have a sustainable business.

Key words: sustainable business, corporate governance, CSR, environment protection, global warming